

Development of a Data Assimilation Framework for Neutronics Design of Novel Reactor Cores

Masahiro TATSUMI^{1,*}, Yasunobu NAGAYA², Kenichi TADA²

¹Nuclear Engineering, Ltd., 1-3-7 Tosabori, Nishi-ku, Osaka 550-0001, Japan

²Japan Atomic Energy Agency, 2-4 Shirakata, Naka-gun, Ibaraki 319-1195, Japan

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803333

ABSTRACT

The development of novel reactor cores challenges neutronics design due to incomplete evaluated nuclear data and declining access to critical integral experiments. We present a data-assimilation framework that systematically integrates archived integral-experiment information, sensitivity data, covariance data, and adjustment tools to quantify and reduce nuclear-data-induced uncertainties for new core concepts without performing new critical experiments. The framework centers on an intermediate data-management layer that imports and indexes sensitivity and covariance input data and produces MARBLE3-compatible data management objects for downstream analysis. MARBLE3 is a modern and Python 3-compatible reactor analysis system that implements various tools including cross-section adjustment tools to update nuclear data consistently and predict post-adjustment uncertainties. Verification using the OECD/NEA SG33 benchmark reproduced reference results, improved calculated-to-experimental agreement, reduced predicted uncertainties, and yielded cross-section adjustments remaining within stated uncertainties. Application to a representative target core produced a breakdown of k_{eff} uncertainty by nuclide and reaction, enabling prioritization of contributors for further study. Current limitations include a fixed energy-group structure and the need for expanded and re-evaluated integral datasets; planned enhancements include dynamic group-transformation capability and systematic database improvements. The proposed framework provides a practical and extensible pathway to assess and improve neutronics prediction accuracy for next-generation reactor cores when new integral experiments are impractical.

Keywords: Data assimilation framework, Nuclear data uncertainty, Cross-section adjustment, Sensitivity analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

To achieve carbon neutrality and energy security, many next-generation reactors including small modular reactors (SMRs) use core configurations, fuels, and moderators that differ substantially from conventional light water reactors (LWRs) and current fast reactors. Evaluated nuclear data for all relevant nuclides are often incomplete, and uncertainties in those data limit the prediction accuracy of core design calculations for these novel concepts compared with mature LWRs and fast designs. Traditionally, critical mockup experiments validated and corrected the core design calculations, but the global decline in experimental facilities makes such validations increasingly difficult.

Data-assimilation techniques offer an alternative by incorporating existing experimental values into core design calculations to reduce parameter uncertainties. Examples include the cross-section adjustment method [1], which is often used in fast-reactor core design, the extended bias-factor method [2], and random-sampling-based methods proposed for LWRs [3, 4]. These methods allow previously accumulated experiments to inform core designs without performing new critical experiments.

* mtatsumi@neltd.co.jp

In this paper, the term “data assimilation” refers to the process of integrating reactor-physics experimental data with computational models and nuclear-data covariances to reduce prediction uncertainties. The cross-section adjustment method is one specific implementation of this broader concept, in which measured integral quantities are used to update multigroup cross-section values through a Bayesian statistical framework.

Despite progress, application of data-assimilation methods to reactor types beyond fast reactors has been limited. Tools like MARBLE [5, 6] provide cross-section adjustment capabilities but are tailored to fast-reactor systems; extending its use-case to other reactor types requires building a new experimental database specific to those systems. Thus, engineers seeking to apply data assimilation to a new reactor core must both gather appropriate reactor-physics experimental data and choose and implement a suitable assimilation method; it would create bottlenecks for them to estimate prediction accuracy of the reactor core.

Therefore, it would be preferable to prepare a framework that combines reactor-physics experimental data, analysis results, sensitivity coefficients, and nuclear-data covariances with a toolset for chosen data-assimilation methods. Such a framework would enable assessment of prediction accuracy for new reactor cores without performing new critical experiments. In this study, we adopt the latest Python 3-compatible version, MARBLE3 [7], as part of that effort.

It should be noted that the novelty of this work does not lie in the cross-section adjustment methodology itself, which is well established [1, 2], but rather in the construction of a modular, extensible data-management and workflow framework. Built on the MARBLE3 code system, this framework systematically organizes experimental data, analysis results, sensitivity coefficients, and covariance matrices, thereby enabling streamlined application of data-assimilation methods to diverse reactor types including novel core concepts.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE PROJECT

The proposed framework is organized across several levels, with a database of integral experimental data as its core. This database will incorporate existing datasets maintained by Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA)—most notably historical FCA and TCA experimental data—as well as burnup sensitivity data and new integral experimental data obtained without nuclear materials. Because parts of the JAEA FCA/TCA datasets remain incompletely curated, a separate project [8] is proceeding in parallel to re-evaluate these experimental data and to reassess their uncertainties. A schematic overview of the framework is shown in Fig. 1.

In addition to JAEA resources, internationally curated repositories such as ICSBEP [9] and IRPhEP [10] will be exploited. These sources supply k_{eff} sensitivity data in TSUNAMI-B format [11]; in particular, they include extensive evaluation results based on a 238-group structure that are expected to be highly valuable for uncertainty assessments within the framework. Complementary efforts to expand and curate the database are being undertaken by partner institutions: Hokkaido University is developing the burnup-sensitivity database, and Nagoya University will perform new integral experiments without nuclear materials.

Operationally, the framework uses reactor analysis and sensitivity analysis codes to perform neutronics calculations for target cores and thereby derive sensitivity data. Sensitivity analyses will primarily be performed using the CBZ code system [12], and the resulting datasets will be imported into the database to conduct uncertainty quantification analyses with data-assimilation and simulation tools (e.g., Python scripts). The overall development and integration of the framework are being led by Nuclear Engineering, Ltd.(NEL), with the objective of systematically managing experimental data, organizing sensitivity-analysis outputs, and quantitatively estimating uncertainties in core design parameters.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the framework for design uncertainty analysis, showing data sources, computational tools, and data-assimilation workflow.

3. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE FRAMEWORK

This chapter briefly describes the architecture of the present framework and implementation policy. The system places the existing uncertainty-analysis and cross-section adjustment capabilities (MARBLE3) at the low layer and implements a newly developed data-management layer above it, thereby facilitating the creation and use of MARBLE3-required data objects such as *SensitivitySet* and *CovarianceSet* (Fig. 2). The primary design focus is to provide a mechanism whereby these data objects can be produced reliably and with minimal effort by users or higher-level systems.

Figure 2. Architecture—MARBLE3 at the low layer, with intermediate managers producing MARBLE3-compatible objects for data assimilation tools from indexed sensitivity and covariance data for user scripts/UI.

The intermediate layer components, *SensitivitySetManager* and *CovarianceSetManager*, imports sensitivity data and covariance data calculated with external codes (e.g., CBZ, FRENDY [13]), store and index sensitivity and covariance data in databases, and extract and compose relevant data in response to user queries to produce MARBLE3-compatible *SensitivitySet* and *CovarianceSet* objects. These managers are callable from Python scripts or higher-level analysis user interfaces (UIs), enabling straightforward integration into custom workflows for data registration, search, and generation.

In the implementation, sensitivity entries are annotated with metadata such as information source (database or experimental case), target nuclear characteristics, nuclide, and reaction type; covariance data are managed with metadata for nuclide and reaction type. The sensitivity database provides indexed, high-speed retrieval of vectors, from which *SensitivitySet* objects are assembled; externally supplied covariance matrices are converted into *CovarianceSet* objects for sharing. The intermediate layer exposes functionality to generate MARBLE3 data classes while remaining decoupled from internal implementation of MARBLE3 to preserve extensibility.

At present the number of energy groups is fixed and a separate database is constructed for each energy-group structure. In future work we plan to provide dynamic transformation capability that can supply sensitivity data for alternative energy-group structures generated from the 238-group dataset.

In summary, the presented framework design aims to realize an intermediate layer that leverages the capabilities of MARBLE3 while making preparation and sharing of sensitivity and covariance data simple and flexible. Through *SensitivitySetManager* and *CovarianceSetManager*, registration, retrieval, transformation, and sharing of data are systematized, enabling efficient data assimilation using *CrossSectionAdjustment* and *UncertaintyPrediction* of MARBLE3.

4. VERIFICATIONS

4.1. Cross-section Adjustment Method

This section briefly reviews the cross-section adjustment method [1] as one of the data-assimilation methods implemented in the framework. The basic data are the sensitivity coefficients and the nuclear-data covariance; The sensitivity coefficients consist of derivatives that quantify how reactor core quantities respond to changes in nuclear data; namely it quantifies “which nuclide/reaction cross section affects which core quantity and by how much.” The nuclear-data covariance describes the uncertainties of nuclear data and their correlations; it is obtained from covariance information in evaluated nuclear data files. Combining these data allows evaluation of nuclear-data-induced covariance in integral quantities of reactor core parameters by the error propagation law: $\text{Cov}(\mathbf{R}) = \mathbf{GMG}^t$, where \mathbf{R} denotes the covariance, \mathbf{G} the sensitivity matrix comprised of sets of sensitivity coefficients, \mathbf{M} the nuclear-data covariance matrix, and t denotes transpose.

The cross-section adjustment method updates a set of nuclear cross sections using experimental data based on the Bayesian theorem to improve the accuracy of core calculations. Specifically, cross sections are adjusted to match integral experimental data via the updates

$$\mathbf{T}' = \mathbf{T} + \mathbf{MG}^t[\mathbf{GMG}^t + \mathbf{V}_e + \mathbf{V}_m]^{-1}[\mathbf{R}_e - \mathbf{R}_c(\mathbf{T})], \quad (1)$$

and

$$\mathbf{M}' = \mathbf{M} - \mathbf{MG}^t[\mathbf{GMG}^t + \mathbf{V}_e + \mathbf{V}_m]^{-1}\mathbf{GM}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{T} is the cross section set, \mathbf{V}_e the experimental uncertainties of integral experiments, \mathbf{V}_m the analytical modeling uncertainties of integral experiments, \mathbf{R}_e the experimental values of integral experiments, and \mathbf{R}_c the calculated values of integral experiments. This approach can incorporate multiple experiments simultaneously and consistently adjust the cross section set within the nuclear data uncertainties.

4.2. Benchmark Calculation

Using the developed data-assimilation framework, we performed an analysis of the OECD/NEA SG33 benchmark [14]. A previous analysis using MARBLE3 exists and serves as a reference. For verification, the benchmark result was reproduced within our framework using *SensitivitySetManager* and *CovarianceSetManager*. Sensitivity data were converted from the legacy SAGEP database to TSUNAMI-B format and then imported into a vector database that can be treated with *SensitivitySetManager*. For covariance data, we did not use datasets produced by the legacy ABLE code; instead we used JENDL-4.0 based covariance data processed with FRENDY. For the covariance data generation, we used the neutron-flux weighting so that it is consistent with the weighting used in the prior MARBLE analyses.

Using these independent data sets and analysis procedures, we reproduced the SG33 benchmark result. After applying the cross-section adjustment method, the agreement between calculated-to-experimental values (C/E) was improved, and the uncertainties were reduced (Fig. 3). The results are consistent with the previous reference analysis, confirming that *SensitivitySetManager* and *CovarianceSetManager* operate as expected. Cross-section adjustments remained within the stated cross-section uncertainties, confirming that the cross-section adjustment mechanism behaves as intended.

In this benchmark analysis, the experimental covariance matrix V_m was constructed based on measurement uncertainties reported in the benchmark documentation supplemented by JAEA internal evaluation values. Since the benchmark specification does not provide a detailed prescription for V_m , the sensitivity of the adjustment results to the assumed experimental uncertainties warrants further investigation. A parametric study of V_m assumptions and their impact on the adjusted results is planned as future work.

To confirm the basic capability of the data-assimilation framework developed in this study, we also calculated the variances in the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} for the target core of the 600 MWe FBR given in the benchmark. With the tools in the framework, we computed $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{M}\mathbf{G}^t$, $\mathbf{G}\mathbf{M}'\mathbf{G}^t$ and $\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{T}' - \mathbf{T})$ to assess the nuclear-data-induced uncertainties before and after the adjustment and the impact on k_{eff} (Δk_{eff}). The results are given in Table I. The contributions to the k_{eff} value were computed by nuclide and reaction type, and ranked in descending order (Fig. 4). Based on this ranking, Fig. 5 presents the alternation of cross sections ordered by their contribution to Δk_{eff} (from largest to smallest).

An important consideration for applying this framework to novel reactor concepts is the representativity of the archived experimental data with respect to the target core. When the neutron spectrum or material composition of the target core differs significantly from those of the benchmark experiments, the effectiveness of the cross-section adjustment may be reduced. Quantitative evaluation of representativity, for example through representativity factors, is not yet implemented in the current version of the framework but is planned for future development. Such capability will be essential for assessing the transferability of experimental knowledge to innovative reactor designs.

Table I. Result of Uncertainties before / after cross-section adjustment and impact on k_{eff}

Item	Value
Before adjustment ($\mathbf{G}\mathbf{M}\mathbf{G}^t$)	0.79%
After adjustment ($\mathbf{G}\mathbf{M}'\mathbf{G}^t$)	0.24%
Δk_{eff}	-0.18%

Figure 3. Comparison of calculated-to-experimental (C/E) values and uncertainties before and after cross-section adjustment for SG33 benchmark cases. The adjusted C/E values are closer to unity with reduced uncertainty bands, demonstrating the effectiveness of the cross-section adjustment.

Figure 4. Breakdown of Δk_{eff} by nuclide and reaction type (600 MWe FBR). The positive contribution from Pu-239 fission spectrum is largely canceled by the negative contribution from U-238 inelastic scattering, and the positive contribution from U-238 capture is offset by the negative contribution from Pu-239 capture. As a result, the net Δk_{eff} is governed by the residual effect of Fe-56 inelastic scattering.

Figure 5. Energy-dependent cross-section alterations and uncertainty bands for the top 9 contributors (600 MWe FBR). The gray bands denote the prior uncertainty ranges. Notable adjustments are observed in the Pu-239 fission spectrum and U-238 capture cross-sections, consistent with the nuclide-reaction ranking in Fig. 4.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We designed and implemented a data-assimilation framework to evaluate and reduce nuclear-data-induced uncertainties in neutron core design of next-generation reactors. The framework centers on an intermediate layer that interfaces with the existing uncertainty-analysis and cross-section adjustment tools in MARBLE3 — namely the *SensitivitySetManager* and *CovarianceSetManager* — and automates registration, indexing, transformation, and generation of MARBLE3-compatible sensitivity and covariance objects. Verification using the OECD/NEA SG33 benchmark showed good agreement with the reference results obtained by MARBLE3. A breakdown of k_{eff} uncertainty for the target core further identified the major contributing nuclides and reactions. The current implementation has limitations, such as a fixed energy-group structure, but these can be addressed by planned improvements including re-evaluation of FCA/TCA data, implementation of dynamic group-transformation functionality, and inclusion of new integral experimental data and burnup-sensitivity datasets. Overall, the proposed framework provides a practical foundation for systematically linking existing experimental resources and analysis tools, and for assessing and reducing design uncertainties for novel reactor cores even when it is difficult to perform new critical experiments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the MEXT Nuclear System Research and Development Program, project JPMXD0224020859.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Cecchini, F. Galligani and M. Salvatores. "Analysis of integral data for few-group parameter evaluation of fast reactor." *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Peaceful Uses Atomic Energy*, Geneva, P/627, 338 (1964).
- [2] T. Kugo, M. Andoh, K. Kojima et al. "Prediction Accuracy Improvement of Neutronic Characteristics of a Breeding Light Water Reactor Core by Extended Bias Factor Methods with Use of FCA-XXII-1 Critical Experiments." *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **45**, pp. 288–303 (2008).
- [3] T. Watanabe, T. Endo, A. Yamamoto et al. "Cross section adjustment method based on random sampling technique." *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **51**, pp. 590–599 (2014).
- [4] T. Endo, A. Yamamoto and T. Watanabe. "Bias factor method using random sampling technique." *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **53**, pp. 1494–1501 (2016).
- [5] K. Yokoyama, M. Tatsumi, Y. Hirai et al. "Development of the Next Generation Reactor Analysis Code System, MARBLE." *JAEA-Data/Code 2010-030* (2011).
- [6] K. Yokoyama and K. Numata. "Development of the Next Generation Code System as an Engineering Modeling Language (VI) – Development of a Cross Section Adjustment and Nuclear Design Accuracy Evaluation Solver." *JAEA-Data/Code 2007-023* (2007).
- [7] K. Yokoyama, T. Hazama, H. Taninaka and S. Ohki. "Development of the Versatile Reactor Analysis Code System, MARBLE3." *JAEA-Data/Code 2024-007* (2024).
- [8] M. Fukushima, M. Ando, Y. Nagaya et al. "Preservation and Utilization of Reactor Physics Experimental Data at Critical Assemblies of Nuclear Science Research Institute of JAEA." 2025 Fall Meeting of the Atomic Energy Society of Japan, Sep. 10 – 12, 2025, 2N08 [in Japanese].
- [9] Nuclear Energy Agency. "International Handbook of Evaluated Criticality Safety Benchmark Experiments 2022/2023." OECD Nuclear Energy Agency, Paris (2024). (NEA No. 7645).
- [10] Nuclear Energy Agency. "International Handbook of Evaluated Reactor Physics Benchmark Experiments 2022/2023." OECD Nuclear Energy Agency, Paris (2024). (NEA No. 7646).
- [11] SCALE User Manual. URL <https://scale-manual.ornl.gov/tsunami-ip-appAB.html>
- [12] G. Chiba, A. Yamamoto and K. Tada. "ACE-FRENDY-CBZ; a new neutronics analysis sequence using multi-group neutron transport calculations." *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **60**, pp. 132–139 (2023).
- [13] K. Tada, A. Yamamoto, S. Kunieda et al. "Development and verification of nuclear data processing code FRENDY version 2." *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **61**, pp. 830–839 (2024).
- [14] Nuclear Energy Agency. "Methods and Issues for the Combined Use of Integral Experiments and Covariance Data." International Evaluation Co-operation, Volume 33, *NEA/NSC/WPEC/DOC(2013)445*, OECD Nuclear Energy Agency, Paris (2013).